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Business Optimization Model of Beef with Plants in the Lowlands in North Mongondow Bolaang

Author's Details: Syarifuddin¹, Budi Hartono², Siti Chuzaemi², Hari Dwi Utami²

¹Animal Science doctoral students of the Graduate Faculty of Animal Husbandry University of Brawijaya, Malang, Indonesia ²Lecturer Doctoral Program of the Graduate Faculty of Animal Husbandry Livestock Brawijaya University, Malang, Indonesia
safruddin@gmail.com

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Abstract

Integrated farming systems are becoming increasingly rational in line with the demands of efficiency and effectiveness of the use of land, labour, capital and production factors is limited. This study with the aim of to analyzes the optimization of integrated farming systems in lowland village Bolaang Sangkub Tombolango District of North Mongondow North Sulawesi province. This study uses a survey to describe the characteristics of the data area and farmers, in the analysis linear programming, Data analysis using software Linear Program Solver (LIPS) and Microsoft Excel. The results showed that 1) The land, capital and labour are a highly influential factor for determining farm income. 2) analysis of the types of businesses in the lowland obtained revenue is the revenue generated in the cattle business optimization-paddy shows the results of the net income of farmers in the lowlands of Rp. 41.89293 million per year, so the farm is highly optimized and well worth the effort. 3) The results of the optimization effort cow-corn-coconut obtain the lowest income of Rp.19,994,054 per year so that the farm is not optimal to be developed

Keywords: *beef, integrated farming, optimal revenue*

I. Introduction

Sector agriculture has a strategic role in supporting the national economy, especially for small and medium empower farmers through agricultural systems. One model of farming is crop-livestock integration. This paradigm requires agriculture's role evolved into not only rely on the major producer of foodstuffs but also biomass materials, feedstock biorefinery to produce food, feed, fertilizer, fibre, energy, pharmaceuticals, chemicals, and other bioproducts(Anonymous, 2014).

Integrated agricultural development, hereinafter called Crop-Livestock Integration System, specialized in rice farming business called the Rice Livestock Integration System, is the intensification of agricultural systems through the management of natural resources and the environment in an integrated manner with the livestock component as part of business activities. Directorate General of Livestock (Anonymous, 2010), describes the integration model developed cattle plants in the location of some regions and countries oriented to the concept of "zero waste production" system that all waste from livestock and crop recycled and reused in the production cycle.

Cattle in northern Sulawesi has been used as a mainstay of the government's livestock area to boost the economic growth of the livestock sector in particular areas. BPS Sulawesi (2016) reported that the number of cattle population in North Sulawesi in 2015 was 119 744 tail, this indicates that there is an increase in the number of cattle population as much as 15 744 head of hasi census report ranch in 2012 as many as 104,000 tails, BPS Sulawesi (Anonymous, 2012).

Cattle development program in North Mongondow Bolaang still be an increase in population. Population enhancement program carried out through the introduction of cattle by the government, while the

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number of the cattle population in the North Mongondow Bolaang as many as 16 387 head, Department of Agriculture (Anonymous, 2016). In reality, the source of cattle in this area still rely on livestock for traditional people management. In general, the cattle business still relies on natural grass that grows freely on farms or plantations. Wild grasses and plant waste used as the main feed for cattle. Biomass production of corn and peanuts so much an enormous potential as cattle feed.

The livestock sector in North Mongondow Bolaang largely a livestock business people (including cattle farming) small scale. Some researchers suggest that most of the cattle business is managed in the form of farm people who are characterized, among others, the number of cattle holdings 1-3 tails every family, a limited land area, maintenance is carried out alone and relatively simple as well as the management of the waste generated is relatively low. Nurdianti et al (2012), describes the development of the people's cattle is done by using agricultural waste. The folk farm development also remains piecemeal with diversification system

Based on the above phenomenon then farm development can be an integrated farming system. The basic concept of system integration cattle (Hand, 2009) is the synergism of integrated farming. Tarnizi and Safaruddin (2012) suggested that the implementation of system integration program can be done through the implementation of a wide range of feed raw materials processing technology and manure as a source of organic fertilizer raw materials. Policy response technology change, greenhouse gas emissions and climate (Leach, 2009) have an impact on world production. Integrated farming (Wulandari, 2014), is the right choice because of the limited ability of agricultural resources. Wahyu (2015), integrated farming is an alternative effort to improve the efficiency of the cattle business in farmland.

The purpose of this study was to analyze the optimization of integrated farming systems in lowland

Based on the results of the previous research that distinguishes this study is the novelty of this research to develop agricultural development model-based optimization of beef cattle breeding business with efficient and optimal crops in the lowlands of North Mongondow Bolaang environmentally friendly

Research methodology

Location and Time Research

The research was conducted in the village of Sangkub Bolaang Tombolango District of North Mongondow North Sulawesi province for six months, namely in February until July 2018. The overall choice of location research using multistage sampling method, but each level location was done in purposive sampling

Village Tombolango District of Sangkub selected as the study site because it is based on Regulation Bolaang Mongondow Utara No. 3 of 2013 About the Spatial Plan Bolaang Mongondow Utara Year 2013-2033 in District Sangkub is an area of farms and ranches, The Farmers have partly already implemented integration efforts cattle with plants, is the largest sub-district of irrigated rice and corn crops, mostly corn plants grown under coconut trees and cattle population 3,265 Most tail as presented in Table 1. The District of Sangkub has 16 villages, while villagers were selected as the study site is the village Tombolango.

Tombolango village located in the lowlands with height 1-25m asl has the largest irrigated rice-fields in the District Sangkub is 632 ha and has been producing liquid and solid organic fertilizer fermented from waste biogas (slurry) is then used to fertilize rice crops and rice straw used as cattle feed, BPP District of Sangkub (Anonymous, 2016).

Sampling

Livestock farmers as respondents determined based on livestock farmers who undertake the production process independently and in groups. Farmers are independent farmers livestock farmers who have cattle at least two adult cows and beef cattle have maintained a minimum of two years, has wetland or corn land and partially planted under coconut trees and never sell cattle. While groups of cattle which a sample is a group that

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already has an enclosure and produces liquid fertilizer / solid. Based on the number of livestock farmers who have these criteria, respondents selected by purposive sampling according to Singarimbun and Effendi (1989) and Suma (2006) that the sample selected intentionally with the intention or certain criteria.

Total cattle population in the village of Tombolango many as 232 ST with the number of cattle ranchers as many as 185 people. The pattern of the farm is cultivated paddy rice, corn, soybeans, and palm. However, the sample in this study is a farmer/rancher related to integrated business activities such as in Table 3.

The number of samples in the study site as many as 327 people, with consideration of costs and time, sampling in this study with purposive sampling technique sampling with specified criteria using the formula Slovin, Sugiono (2010). The sample size is calculated using the formula Slovin in Uma (2003), namely;

$$n \dots\dots\dots (1) = \frac{N}{N(e)^2 + 1}$$

Information:

- n : Number of samples
- N : The number of population
- e : Precision used 10% which is the level of deviation from the characteristics of the sample to the population

$$n = \frac{327}{327(0,1)^2 + 1}$$

= 44

The result using a sample obtained Slovin formula breeders as many as 44 people. The number of samples of farmers in each group is determined proportionally by the following formula (Sugiono, 2014).

Data analysis

Research results will be tabulated and analyzed by following the purpose of the research is analyzed *linear programming* to optimize revenue beef cattle business with plants in the lowland village Tombolango in North Mongondow Bolaang

Siswanto, (2002), the linear programming approach is described as follows:

1. Model

The objective function can be expressed mathematically as follows:

$$\text{Maximum } Z = C_1X_1 + C_2X_2 + \dots + C_jX_j + \dots + C_nX_n$$

The limiting factor:

1. Land: $A_i \leq \sum a_{ij}X_j$
2. Labor: $\sum b_{ij}X_j \leq B_i$
3. Working Capital : $\sum d_{ij}X_j \leq D_i$

Information:

- Z = The advantages that should be maximized
- Xj = Optimal Size of business type j (Ha)
- cj = The gain from this type of business to j (USD / year)
- Ai = The total area of agricultural land available
- a_{ij} = Input-output coefficients cultivated land area
- Bi = Day of the work (HOK) is available from any farmer households (HOK / Year)

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bij = The need for labour every type of business (HOK/year)

In = Working capital which of each farmer households

dij = The need for working capital every type of business

i = 1,2,3, ..., m

j = 1,2,3, ..., n

2. Constraints and Activity Model

a. Dryland (LK)

Dryland in question is land used for the production of beef cattle, corn, dry rice, soybean and coconut, forage and other crops. Area of land controlled by peasant owners or tenants is assumed to average 0.5 ha.

b. Wetlands (LB)

A wetland is land used for the production of beef cattle and rice crops. Area of land controlled by peasant owners or tenants is assumed to average 0.5 ha.

c. Manpower (TK)

Family labour availability is limited, so it will be an obstacle in carrying out its activities. Number of family labour available is calculated based on the number of people working in farming (HOK). A value of 1 HOK in the research area equivalent to 7 hours, starting at 07:30 until 11:30 and 14:00 until 17:00.

d. Capital

Self-owned capital is calculated based on the average capital belongs to the farmers who used for farming, based on information obtained from the farmers. These capital constraints specified per month and are expressed in units rupiah (Rp).

Results and Discussion

Optimization is done on integrated farming systems in the lowlands between the cattle-rice (*Bos sondaicus-Oryza sativa*), Cow-corn (*Oos sondaicus-Zea mays*), Beef-rice-maize (*Oryza sondaicus- boss sativa-Zea mays*), Cow-corn-oil (*Bos sondaicus-Zea mays-Cocos nucifera*), Beef-rice-soy (*Bos sondaicus - Oryza sativa - Gycine max*) There are three constraints in the optimization of the constraints of land, labour and capital. The first obstacle is the land area that is the basis for the establishment of optimization.

Preparation of the objective function and constraints

Optimization analysis was performed using the Linear Program Solver (Lips). The survey and interview respondents obtained four cropping and cattle business fairly dominant farmers in the research area. The farmers cultivated commodity is business as rice, corn, coconut and soybeans, to determine the optimal combination of maintenance optimization cattle. Results of the research are the initial condition is a picture in the field where these conditions serve as the basis for step determining optimization measures or the preparation of sustainable cattle business.

The cropping pattern and the cattle business respondents indicted farmers do not optimal in utilizing existing resources to achieve the goal of sustainability. Target objectives to be achieved in this study was to determine revenue optimization farmers beef cattle business with plants in the lowlands. Based on cropping patterns, there is four variabel decision as follows:

X1: optimized paddy acreage (ha)

X2: optimized corn acreage (ha)

X3: coconut optimized total area (ha)

X4: optimized soybean acreage (ha)

The purpose of optimization to be obtained is to increase farmers' net income (USD / year)

Constraints there are three, namely:

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K1: Constraints limited land (ha)

K2: Constraints limited capital (US \$ / ha / yr)

K3: Obstacles to labour shortages family (HOK/ha/yr)

Decision-making is done on the types of commodities namely rice (X1), corn (X2), coconut (X3) and soybeans (X4).

Table 1. Constraints The area of land in the Lowlands Rural Tombolango (ha)

Crop type	The land area on the pattern of farming (ha)					mean
	SP	SJ	SPJ	SJKa	spke	
paddy	2.10		1.00		2.00	1.70
Corn		1.38	1.00	1.63		1.34
Coconut				1.63		1.63
Soy					0.50	0.50
Total	2.10	1.38	2.00	3.26	2.50	
Owned land	4.69	1.73	2.38	3.26	2.40	2.89

Source: Adapted from primary data (Appendix 3)

Table 1 shows that the average area of land use based commodities in the widest lowland paddy is an area of 1.70 ha, while the average consumption is at least soybean with an area of 0.50 ha. The first obstacle can be formulated as follows:

$$K1: X1 + X2 + X3 + X4 + X5 \leq 2.89$$

The second constraint is the constraint of labour and family daily labour. In Table 2 presented family labour and daily labour for one- hectare area business pattern.

Table 2. Labour Constraints on Lowland Village Tombolango

Crop type	TKK in farming patterns (HOK/ha/yr)					mean
	SP	SJ	SPJ	SJKa	spke	
Total Land Use	2.93	1.38	2.00	3.26	2.06	
Family labour ((HOK						
paddy	1,980	-	360	-	140	827
Corn		385	315	455	-	385
Coconut				260		260
Soy					140	140

Source: Adapted from the primary data, 2018

Table 2, explaining that family labour (TKK) per hectare of area businesses, this suggests that the use of family labour in the lowlands there are efforts paddy using family labour more averaging 827 HOK / ha, and soybean using family labour, the lowest with an average of 140 person-days / h, or to an area of 2.98 ha needed family work an average of 1,165 person-days. A second constraint can be formulated as follows:

$$K2: 827x1 + 385x2 + 260x3 + 140x4 \leq 1,165$$

The third obstacle is venture capital constraints. In Table 6 are presented effort for one-hectare area business pattern.

Table 3. Venture Capital Constraints on Lowland Village Tombolango

Crop type	Each pattern farm venture capital (US \$ / ha / yr)					mean
	SP	SJ	SPJ	SJKa	spke	

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			26.83			
paddy	22,216,364	-	million	-	26,964,615	25,336,993
Corn		19,618,182	21.1 million	22,023,077		20,913,753
Coconut				16,046,971		16,046,971
Soy					13.5785	13.5785
					million	million

Source: Adapted from the primary data, 2018

Table 3 explains that the capital of each commodity in the lowlands are the highest capital absorption in the paddy which is an average of Rp. 25,336,993, the lowest capital absorption soybean which is an average of Rp. 13.5785 million, so for a low-lying area of 2.89 ha in average working capital is Rp. 54,820,567. A third constraint can be formulated as follows:

$$K3 : 25.336.993x1 + 20.913.753x2 + 16.046.971x3 + 13.578.500x4 \leq 54,820,567$$

function Purpose

The objective function is to describe the Objective to be achieved and expressed in a linear function. Maximizing the net income of farmers and minimize production costs per hectare per year. Based on the survey results and tabulations of data every farming patterns related to the four types of crops that have been enhanced with the planting area (US \$ / ha/yr). Exposure can result in farmers' net income presented in Table 7.

Table 4. Net Income of Farmers Produced at Each pattern Farming for One Year.

type of plant	Net income of farmers in farming patterns (USD / year/ha)					mean
	SP	SJ	SPJ	SJKa	spke	
paddy	28.76 million	-	18.77 million	-	18,635,385	22,055,128
Corn		21.87532 million	12.6 million	11,276,923		15,250,748
Coconut				8576106		8576106
Soy					9.9304 million	9.9304 million
beef cattle	7707543	6722636	4938665	4179983	4219071	5.55358 million
Cow-Rice	36,467,543					36,467,543
Cow-Corn		28,597,956				28,597,956
Ox-Rice-Corn			36,308,665			36,308,665
Ox-Corn-Oil				24,033,012		24,033,012
Ox-Rice-Soybean					32,784,856	32,784,856

Source: Adapted from the primary data, 2018

based on Table 4 it can be seen that net income in the cattle business lowland rice are the highest income which is an average of Rp.36,467,543 per year, while the average net income of a business-corn-oil cow is the lowest is Rp. 24,033,012 per year.

$$Q: \text{Max}: 36.467.543X1 + X2 + 36,308,665 28,597,956 24,033,012 X3 + X4 + X5 32,784,856$$

Completion of Linear Programming Optimizati

Linear programming is a form of technical analysis using mathematical equations model that serves to assist in achieving the goal, Hartono (2016). The objective function (optimization) and constraint functions in this study can be solved by Linear Programming. Completion by using software Linear Program Solver (LIPS) and Microsoft Excel. as follows:

Table 5. Results of Optimization Cow-Rice with Functions Goals and Constraints Defined

Function	Symbol	Solutions	
Decision	Cow	0	ST
	paddy	2.06	Ha
Purpose	Net income	41,892,930.00	rp
	number of Livestock	8.86	ST
	Compost	89634.80	kg / head / yr
	Agricultural waste	6647.00	kg / ha / yr
Obstacles	Land	1.40	Ha
	Labor	126.00	HOK
	Capital	41,862,699.41	rp

Source: Data were analyzed, 2019

Recommend planting rice area of 2.06 ha, which will produce the following objectives:

1. The highest net revenue reaching Rp. 41.89293 million per year
2. Increasing the number of animals kept as much as 8.86 ST per year
3. Utilization of waste manure for fertilizer as much as 89 634 kg per year
4. Utilization of agricultural wastes as animal feed as much as 6647 kg per year

Under the conditions of the study area on the lowland village of Tombolango a business development area irrigated paddy fields because there are technical so the availability of animal feed from agricultural waste is abundant, but only a small part is used. Wantasen and Papatungan (2017) show the results of the research that the larger scale cattle ownership greater added value is obtained, the average value added per unit of cattle Rp. 4,435,543 per year.

Table 6. Results Optimization-Corn Beef with objective function and constraints Defined

Function	Symbol	Solutions	
Decision	Cow	1.00	ST
	Corn	2.09	Ha
Purpose	Net income	28,597,956.00	rp
	number of Livestock	5.32	ST
	Compost	15700.24	kg / head / yr
	Agricultural waste	2125.62	kg / ha / yr
Obstacles	Land	1.38	Ha
	Labor	106.00	HOK
	Capital	36,221,983.13	rp

Source: Data were analyzed, 2019

Recommend maintaining cattle 1.00 ST and planted corn area of 2.09 ha, which will produce the following objectives:

1. The highest net revenue reaching Rp. 28,597,956 per year
2. Increasing the number of animals kept as much as 5.32 ST per year
3. Utilization of waste manure for fertilizer as much as 15,700 kg per year
4. Utilization of agricultural wastes as animal feed as many as 2,125 kg per year

Table 7

Results of Optimization Cow-Rice-Corn Objective Function and Constraints Defined

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Function	Symbol	Solutions	
Decision	Cow	0	ST
	paddy	2.89	Ha
	Corn	0	Ha
Purpose	Net income	36,308,665.00	rp
	number of Livestock	4.65	ST
	Compost	12446.11	kg / head / yr
	Agricultural waste	1859.36	kg / ha / yr
Obstacles	Land	2.00	Ha
	Labor	205.00	HOK
	Capital	64,740,247.25	rp

Source: Data were analyzed, 2019

Recommend a plant area of 2.89 ha of rice and corn crops are not recommended, so that it will produce the following objectives:

1. The highest net revenue reaching Rp. 36,308,665 per year
2. Increasing the number of animals kept as much as 4.65 ST per year
3. Utilization of waste as manure for fertilizer 12446.11 kg per year
4. Utilization of agricultural wastes as animal feed as 1,859,36 kg per year

Table 8. Results of Optimization Cow-Corn-Oil with Objective Function and Constraints Defined

Function	Symbol	Solutions	
Decision	Cow	0	ST
	Corn	1.77	Ha
	Coconut	0	Ha
Purpose	Net income	19,994,054.00	rp
	number of Livestock	4.04	ST
	Compost	12461.46	kg / head / yr
	Agricultural waste	12641.09	kg / ha / yr
Obstacles	Land	3.26	Ha
	Labor	166.00	HOK
	Capital	54,131,988.16	rp

Source: Data were analyzed, 2019

Recommend measuring 1.77 hectares to grow corn and coconut plants is not recommended so that it will produce the following objectives:

1. The highest net revenue reaching Rp. 19,994,054per year
2. Increasing the number of animals kept as much as 4.04 ST per year
3. Utilization of waste as manure for fertilizer 12461.46kg per year
4. Utilization of agricultural wastes as animal feed as many as 12641.09 kg per year

Several studies have been conducted in North Sulawesi, including by Elly (2008), Salendu (2012) and Rundengan (2013). All three studies have been conducted that discusses the integration of cattle and coconut,. Plants coconut plantation crops can adapt to the environment and can be grown in the tropics, but in the study on lowland village Tombolango a technical irrigation area so the land for the cultivation of paddy rice takes precedence over the coconut plantations.

Table 9. Results of Optimization Cow-Rice-Soybean with objective function and constraints Defined

Function	Symbol	Solutions	
Decision	Cow	0	ST

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	paddy	1.18	Ha
	Soy	1.91	Ha
	Net income	41,072,782.00	rp
Purpose	number of Livestock	6.51	ST
	Compost	45082.05	kg / head / yr
	Agricultural waste	1301.05	kg / ha / yr
Obstacles	Land	2.06	Ha
	Labor	166.00	HOK
	Capital	55,181,348.94	rp

Source: Data were analyzed, 2019

Recommend planting rice area of 1.18 ha and a soybean crop of 1.91 ha, which will produce the following objectives:

1. The highest net revenue reaching Rp. 41,072,782 per year
2. Increasing the number of animals kept as much as 6.51 ST per year
3. Utilization of waste as manure for fertilizer 45082.05 kg per year
4. Utilization of agricultural wastes as animal feed as many as 1301.05kg per year

Conclusion

Based on the analysis and discussion that has been described, it can be summed up as follows:

1. Area of land, capital and labour are the highly influential factor determining farm incomes (Ox-rice, cow-corn, rice-corn-cow, cow-corn-oil and cattle-rice-soy).
2. Revenue generated in the cattle business optimization-rice showed the highest net revenue yields in lowland farmers Rp. 41.89293 million per year or equivalent to Rp. 3,422,732 per month, it shows that this business is optimal and meets the Living Needs (KHL) and the amount is already more with UMP North Sulawesi in 2019 of Rp. 3,150,000 per month
3. Business optimization results cow-corn-coconut obtain the lowest income of Rp. 19,994,054 per year or equivalent to Rp. 1,666,171 per month. This effort shows that do not meet the Living Needs (KHL) and the magnitude of the UMP in North Sulawesi.

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